

**COMMITMENT TO GRADUATE SCHOOLING AS A PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS FROM THE DIVISION
OF QUEZON**

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Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development of Teachers from the Division of Quezon

Maureen V. Garcia*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research delves in assessing the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development of teachers from the division of Quezon and propose a professional development plan. It used a descriptive-comparative type of research under quantitative design utilizing a validated survey questionnaire for this study with demographic profile, level of commitment to graduate schooling and degree of agreement on the frequency of encountered difficulties with 5-Point Likert Scales. Teachers were highly committed to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework; teachers often encounter difficulties pursuing graduate degrees as a Continuing Professional Education. Using frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and Kruskal Wallis H-Test, the result showed that the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to profile is statistically significant except for civil status and designation. In contrast, the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to profile is not statistically significant. As for the degree of agreement on the frequency of encountered difficulties, the result showed that problems encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age was not statistically significant except for civil status and years in service both under the family commitments while going to school which showed statistically significant result. As an output, the researcher prepared a professional development plan to provide teachers with an avenue to comprehend the different dimensions of professional development. Thus, through the teacher's development plan output, they will grasp information and relevant readings that they employ to continuously keep updated in the latest trends of educational practices even though they are not enrolled in a graduate school program.

Keywords: *continuing professional education, degree of agreement, graduate schooling, level of commitment*

Introduction

With DepEd's adoption of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) which articulates a higher level of standards for teachers that may be developed in graduate studies, the graduate schooling is more critical than ever. The Policies and Standards for Graduate Programs (PSG) in Education for Teachers and Other Education Professionals (CHED Memorandum Order No. 53, series of 2007) explains that graduate studies in teacher education are an effective means of improving the capacities of education professionals who aim to contribute to educational processes like teaching and management of educational programs. The professional commitment of employees is related to the effort they put into doing their jobs. Therefore, professional commitment significantly affects employees' performance on the job. As with other employees, teachers' professional commitment level is effective in their performance (Meriq, 2020).

In the globally changing world, where new knowledge and technologies emerge daily, the gap between what individuals know and what they need to know is ever-widening (Robinson & Aronica, 2015, as cited in Hollinger & Larwin, 2019). Therefore, to thrive, adults must learn. Adult learning can range from watching YouTube videos to gaining new skills to studying for advanced degrees. In the background of global change, the knowledge systems of our graduate students today must demonstrate flexibility and innovation, while still maintaining their commitments (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 2011, as cited in Badidles, 2021). Motivation is the core reason for graduate students' actions, desires, and needs. Willingness to acquire better expertise in the field of study, thirst for higher qualification and the need to meet requirements for a choice career are needed factors in motivating oneself to finish post-graduate studies (Fadairo & Ogundipe, 2016).

In the Regional perspective, with regards to the focus and main goals of Professional Development (PD), authors such as Borko (2024) and Desimone et al. (2022) conceive teacher PD to be an essential mechanism for enhancing teachers' knowledge and instructional practices. Bringing about changes in teachers' attitudes and beliefs is, for authors like Guskey (2022), another major objective of PD. More recently, authors such as Kazemi and Hubbard (2018) and Opfer and Peder (2021) have emphasized the need for more complex understandings, arguing that PD has the potential to impact many aspects of teachers' professional and personal lives, impacting teachers' knowledge, competences, and values. In this study, the researcher subscribes to the definition proposed by Avalos (2021), as it nicely articulates several relevant topics that have been discussed in recent years by researchers in the field. As captured in Avalos' definition, the researcher considers that the focus and ultimate goal of teacher PD should be the benefit of students' learning and achievement.

In the local setting, enrolling in a graduate course entails sacrifices, challenges, and opportunities. In the context of the teaching

profession, teachers are encouraged to attend graduate schools to improve their status, productivity, and income given the nature of work demands and academic pressure (Zulieta et. al, 2019). According to Arrieta et al. (2019), it is imperative that pursuing higher education increases one's caliber as a professional, strengthening specs that eventually lead to promotion and higher leverage at work. Ryan and Zuber-Skerritt (2017) also agree that what graduates learn in the education process equips them later to work as academics, researchers, or professionals in leading positions. Even without great breakthroughs, achieving mastery of a subject or discipline can be a great pleasure in and of itself. Although higher degree leads to stronger career opportunities, greater financial stability, and positive outcomes, teachers often discontinue their chosen graduate program.

In the report of CHED from the academic year 2015-2016 to 2017-2018, the average number of graduates in master's level is 29,876.33 which is 15.64% against the average enrollment of 90,944.66. The attrition rate is significantly high. The data given above, suggests that various factors may have contributed to the decrease in the number of graduates at the master's level and indicates the lack of commitment of graduate students including serious issues and concerns related to the policies and processes in the graduate program. Several empirical studies revealed that teachers' commitment is largely influenced by the administrative policies of the school and the work environment (Baron & Greenberg, 2020). Support from administrators will greatly increase their work achievement and commitment as well as substantial job satisfaction (Salimon, 2023). However, if they are burdened with too many non-academic duties, they lose their commitment to their pursuit of professional development (Ball & Goodson, 2015).

The researcher, as a graduate student also, would like to know how committed graduate students are to finishing their degree. To reiterate, the average number of graduates in the master's level is 29,876.33 which is 15.64% against the average enrollment of 90,944.66. The attrition rate is significantly high. Moreover, the study wanted to investigate the commitment to Graduate Schooling as a professional development of teachers in the Division of Quezon. This examined how the teachers enroll in graduate schooling for promotions and career development as a lifelong learning commitment. Also, the researcher would like to come up with results that will provide a broader understanding of the purpose of obtaining such degrees. With a better understanding of their commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development, graduate students can use this as a reminder for completing their courses, as well as for keeping themselves driven in taking the difficult studies and research.

Research Questions

Generally, this study tried to assess the level of commitment to graduate schooling and difficulties encountered by teacher respondents from the division of Quezon, it sought to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. years in service;
 - 1.5. teacher rank; and
 - 1.6. Units earned in master's or doctorate degree?
2. What is the level of commitment of the respondents to graduate schooling as articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework in terms of:
 - 2.1. master's degree:
 - 2.1.1. advanced knowledge and skills;
 - 2.1.2. self-directed research;
 - 2.1.3. lifelong learning; and
 - 2.1.4. application of skills?
 - 2.2. doctorate degree:
 - 2.2.1. demonstration of highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills;
 - 2.2.2. utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice;
 - 2.2.3. application of more complex settings; and
 - 2.2.4. Application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability?
3. Is there any significant difference in the level of commitment to graduate schooling when they are grouped according to profile?
4. What is the degree of difficulties encountered in graduate schooling in terms of:
 - 4.1. financing the study;
 - 4.2. school requirements;
 - 4.3. family commitments while going to school;
 - 4.4. thesis requirements;
 - 4.5. balancing work and study; and
 - 4.6. location of graduate school?
5. Is there any significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by respondents in graduate schooling when they are grouped according to profile?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive type of research. Calderon (2020) defines descriptive research as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretations about such data with or without or sometimes minimal aid of statistical methods. This described the teachers' demographic profile, teachers' level of commitment to graduate schooling as professional development, and difficulties encountered by the teachers in pursuing graduate schooling as professional development. This is found appropriate since the study was centered on the commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development of second congressional district elementary school teachers of Quezon which would come up with a professional development plan.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were elementary teachers from different schools in the second congressional district of Quezon. They were randomly selected to participate in the study. Only five (5) municipalities or districts in the Second Congressional District of Quezon were included and selected in this undertaking since Lucena City has its division. Teachers were picked through the criteria set by the researcher to assess their commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development. The public school elementary teachers were teachers who are currently teaching and still in the service with permanent plantilla allocation or regular teaching positions from Teacher 1 to Teacher III, Master Teacher 1 to Master Teacher III, and Head Teacher I in the schools. These teachers were the subject of research since they are the ones required to be enrolled in the Graduate Schooling where the researcher takes this as an opportunity for them to participate in this study through intrinsic motivation. Aside from that, these teachers were persuaded to participate in the conduct of the study through incentives given to them. This is depicted in the following table and computations.

Here, the study employed a simple random technique. Simple random sampling is a type of probability sampling in which the researcher randomly selects a subset of participants from a population. Each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. Data is then collected from as large a percentage as possible of this random subset (Calderon, 2020).

The respondents of the study were the Master's and Doctoral students enrolled in graduate schooling. Moreover, these were male and female, ranging from twenty (20) to fifty-nine (59) years old. These are found appropriate since they are the teachers who need to comply with the Continuing Professional Development and their Career Development in the Second District of Quezon.

Instrument

To come up with a strong and valid data, the researcher crafted the research instruments along with relevant legal bases and theories. Survey questionnaires were crafted for the purpose of the study, and was validated by a Doctor in Education, an English Teacher and an expert in graduate schooling. The design aimed to gather and established evidence on the teachers' commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development in the Second District of Quezon.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission and endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Quezon. After getting the superintendent's approval, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the different school principals and heads of all the elementary schools. To encourage the respondents, incentives were given. Also, the researcher personally visited and asked for help from the school's research coordinator to administer the questionnaire. The researcher explained the importance of this study to cultivate their interest and motivation and to elicit their cooperation and consent. The initial gathering of survey questionnaires was made possible through Google Forms due to the risk brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. This was followed by the ethics clearance by sending informed consent to the respondents. There are also inclusion and exclusion criteria involved. The inclusion criteria were how the respondents find respondents who would answer for the study. The exclusion criteria were how they encountered some refusal where the respondents found another respondent who would participate. However, the researcher personally distributed and retrieved the questionnaires from those internet-challenged schools located too far. The data were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted with guidance from the adviser and statistician.

Ethical Considerations

At all times, the researcher observed the integrity of the research by following professional ethics. Respect for the dignity of research participants was prioritized. Full consent was obtained from the participants prior to the study. Confidentiality and protection of the privacy of research respondents was ensured as well as the anonymity of individuals and organizations participating in the study.

Participation in the study was voluntary and respondents had the right to withdraw at any time. Any deception or exaggeration about the aims and objectives of the research were avoided. Any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. Any type of misleading information was avoided and use of offensive, discriminatory, or other unacceptable language were negated in the formulation of the study and the questionnaire.

The study has the highest standard in complying and attaining the provisions on the Privacy Statement and Data Privacy Act so that all

the human subject or participants are protected as they share or give their responses needed for the study. Anonymity was treated strictly in the study to cover the confidentiality of information and be able to maintain such confidentiality as provided in the study so that all information will be subjected for research purposes only and not otherwise. Disposal of information followed the rule of Data Privacy Act in disposing the unneeded, unused, and already used information to be junked.

Results and Discussion

This is composed of five parts. The first part is comprised of the profile of the respondents. The second part discusses the level of commitment of the respondents to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework for Master's and Doctorate Degrees. The third part tackles the test for significant differences in the level of commitment of the respondents to graduate schooling as a professional development when they are grouped according to profile. The fourth part explains the encountered difficulties in graduate schooling as a professional development. The last part elucidated that test for significant differences in the difficulties encountered by the respondents in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when they are grouped according to profile.

1. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Years in Service, Designation, and Units Earned in Master's Degree

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age*

Age (in years)	Master's		Doctoral		Total	
	F	%	F	%	f	%
21-30	46	33.6	1	0.7	47	34.3
31-40	41	29.9	13	9.5	54	39.4
41-50	25	18.2	1	0.7	26	19.0
51-60	9	6.6	1	0.7	10	7.3
Total	121	88.3	16	11.7	137	100.0

Table 1 shows the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of age. Most of the respondents are between the age of 31 to 40 years old with a frequency of fifty-four (54) or 39.40%. Next are those between the ages of 21 to 30 years old having a frequency of forty-seven (47) or 34.30%. Those who are between the ages 41 to 50 years old got a frequency of twenty-six (26) or 19%. Ten (10) respondents are 51 to 60 years old.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex*

Civil Status	Master's		Doctoral		Total	
	F	%	F	%	f	%
Single	32	23.4	6	4.4	38	27.7
Married	86	62.8	10	7.3	96	70.1
Widowed	3	2.2	0	0.0	3	2.2
Total	121	88.3	16	11.7	137	100.0

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of civil status. A majority of the respondents were married individuals with a frequency of 96 (70.10%). Following were those single with a frequency of 38, or an equivalent percentage of 27.70%. Three respondents were widowed.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Years in Service*

Years in Service (in years)	Master's		Doctoral		Total	
	f	%	F	%	f	%
0-5	39	28.5	1	0.7	40	29.2
6-10	31	22.6	3	2.2	34	24.5
11-15	15	10.9	11	8.0	26	19.0
16-20	25	18.2	0	0.0	25	18.2
21-25	6	4.4	0	0.0	6	4.4
Over 26	5	3.6	1	0.7	6	4.4
Total	121	88.3	16	11.7	137	100.0

Table 3 shows the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of years in service. Forty (40) or 29.20% of the respondents serve the school for 0 to 5 years. This is followed by those who serve for 6 to 10 years having a frequency of thirty-four (34) or 24.50%. Those who served for 11 to 15 years get a frequency of twenty-six (26) or 19.00%. Those who served under the bracket of 16 to 20 years have a frequency of twenty-five (25) or 18.20%. Six (6) respondents tie with the brackets of 21 to 25 years and over 26 years.

Table 4. Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Teacher Rank

Designation	Master's		Doctoral		Total	
	f	%	F	%	f	%
Teacher 1	73	53.3	0	0.0	73	53.3
Teacher 2	27	18.2	2	1.5	27	19.7
Teacher 3	30	13.9	11	8.0	19.7	21.9
Master Teacher 1	5	2.2	2	1.5	3.6	3.6
Master Teacher 2	2	0.7	1	0.7	1.5	1.5
Total	121	88.3	16	11.7	137	100.0

Table 4 shows the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of years designation. The majority of the respondents are in the Teacher 1 position with a frequency of seventy-three (73) or 53.30%. This is followed by the Teacher 2 position having a frequency of twenty-seven (27) or 19.70%. Teacher 3 position gets a frequency of twenty (20), or 21.90%. Those in the Master Teacher 1 position register a frequency of four (4) or 3.60%. Two (2) respondents are in the Master Teacher 2 position.

Table 5. Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Units Earned

Units Earned (in units)	Master's		Doctorate		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
0-9	9	6.6	0	0.0	9	6.6
10-18	10	7.3	2	1.5	12	8.8
19-27	15	10.9	1	0.7	16	11.7
28-36	54	39.4	4	2.9	58	42.3
37-45	24	17.5	4	2.9	28	20.4
46 and above	9	6.6	5	3.6	14	10.2
Total	121	88.3	16	11.7	137	100.0

Table 5 below shows the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of units earned. Most of the respondents earn 28 to 36 units with a frequency of fifty-eight (58) or 42.30%. This is followed by those who earned 37 to 45 units having a frequency of twenty-eight (28), or 20.40%. Those who earned 19 to 27 units have a frequency of sixteen (16) or 11.70%. Those who earned 46 units and above got a frequency of fourteen (14) or 10.20%. Earning 10 to 18 units registers a frequency of twelve (12) or 8.80%. Nine (9) respondents earn 0 to 9 units.

2. Level of Commitment of the Respondents to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework for Master's and Doctorate Degrees

Table 6 below shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents in terms of Advanced Knowledge and Skills. The grand mean is 4.06 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly Committed." This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents. This could imply that more teachers are inclined to enroll in Graduate Schooling for promotions and career development opportunities.

Table 6. Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling in terms of Advanced Knowledge and Skills

Advanced Knowledge and Skills	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that...		
1 I can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for written communication in a second language.	4.32	Highly Committed
2 I can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for comprehension in a second language.	4.12	Highly Committed
3 I can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for oral communication.	4.00	Highly Committed
4 I can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for comprehension in the first language.	3.97	Highly Committed
5 I can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for statistics and interpretation of data.	3.88	Highly Committed
Grand Mean:	4.06	Highly Committed

Legend: "Not Committed (1.00 - 1.50)," "Barely Committed (1.51 - 2.50)," "Moderately Committed (2.51 - 3.50)," "Highly Committed (3.51 - 4.50)," "Very Highly Committed (4.51 - 5.00)"

The highest indicator stated that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for written communication in a second language" with a mean of 4.32. This means that the respondents can be acquainted with written communication using second language. This is followed by the indicator eliciting that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for comprehension in a second language" with a mean of 4.12. This

indicates that the respondents can understand second language as used in a context. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for oral communication” with a mean of 4.00. This implies that the respondents could acquire fluency in oral communication as used and applied. The lowest indicator elicits that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can develop advanced knowledge and skills required for statistics and interpretation of data” with a mean of 3.88. This means that the respondents can develop competencies in using or employing statistics for the interpretation of data in a paper or manuscript.

These findings align with the DepEd’s adoption of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) which articulates a higher level of standards for teachers that may be developed in graduate studies, the role of graduate education is more critical than ever. The Policies and Standards for Graduate Programs (PSG) in Education for Teachers and Other Education Professionals (CHED Memorandum Order No. 53, series of 2007) explains that graduate studies in teacher education are an effective means of improving the capacities of education professionals who aim to contribute to educational processes like teaching and management of educational programs. Moreover, the recent policies, Standards, and Guidelines for Graduate Programs (CHED Memorandum Order No. 15, series of 2019) articulate that graduate programs have the role of spurring and sustaining advanced competencies like creative and effective learning and teaching, scientific and technological growth, and leadership and innovation. Thus, there is a need for graduate teacher education programs to have the qualities that can meet the demands of the educational reforms and societal issues that the country is currently experiencing (Miranda, 2021).

Also, Skidmore (2007, as cited in Habib, 2019) defines professionally committed teachers are those teachers who are dedicated to developing themselves professionally by seeking advanced degrees and standards-based professional growth opportunities, critically reflective in their practice by seeking meaningful feedback and discourse, and engagement in action research, and advancing the teaching profession through the creation of professional learning communities and teachers’ contributions to leadership positions.

Table 7. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Master’s Respondents in terms of Self-Directed Research*

	Self-Directed Research	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the initiative with or without the help of others so that...		
1	I can diagnose research needs of my school, the immediate community, the country, and the world.	3.93	Highly Committed
2	I can formulate research goals and objectives appropriate for the chosen topic.	3.70	Highly Committed
3	I can identify resources needed for a research project.	3.74	Highly Committed
4	I can choose and implement appropriate strategies needed for the completion of a research project.	3.75	Highly Committed
5	I can evaluate the impact of research on the intended users and beneficiaries.	3.81	Highly Committed
	Grand Mean:	3.79	Highly Committed

Legend: “Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50),” “Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50),” “Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50),” “Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 7 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master’s respondents in terms of Self-Directed Research. The grand mean is 3.79 with a verbal interpretation of “Highly Committed.” This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master’s respondents. This implies that teachers were engaged in educational research be it for Graduate Schooling or Classroom Settings.

The highest response showed that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the initiative with or without the help of others so that the respondents can diagnose research needs of their school, the immediate community, the country, and the world” with a mean of 3.93. This means that the respondents can observe a problem they are apprehensive at and be able to conduct research. Next is the item stating that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the initiative with or without the help of others so that the respondents can evaluate the impact of research on the intended users and beneficiaries” with a mean rating of 3.81. This means that the respondents know to determine the effect or impact of research on the targeted users or beneficiaries for them to be able to utilize the output or outcome of the research. Ranking third is the statement eliciting that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the initiative with or without the help of others so that the respondents can choose and implement appropriate strategies needed for the completion of a research project” with a mean of 3.75. This implies that the respondents have long-range strategic plans for the conduct of a research project.

The lowest response indicates that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the initiative with or without the help of others so that the respondents can formulate research goals and objectives appropriate for the chosen topic” with a mean of 3.70. This shows that the respondents could deduce research goals and objectives on a given topic or research problem they felt they were apprehensive about.

These results are in connection with the fact that teaching is not an easy task, and it demands a high degree of professional qualities

and commitment which is inculcated in the teacher's personality. Scholars in the field of education all over the world have started realizing that it is not sufficient to secure enough teachers, but that the most important is securing the right type of teachers with the right type of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. A committed teacher is focused and more involved in her/his profession. At times, it is presumed that teachers are committed and devoted to their profession, although this is not always the case. It has been sometimes noted that even though the line of work has been chosen voluntarily by teachers, commitment tends to decrease after some time. Lower commitment affects the effectiveness of schools and causes teachers to be less successful in their professional performance or to leave the profession in extreme cases (Hussen, 2021). Moreover, to understand an adult's commitment to partake and persist in formal learning experiences, the decision-making process to initiate formal learning, exit formal learning, and reengage in formal learning must be explored to identify mechanisms to assist adult learners in the completion of their personal formal learning goals (Hollinger & Larwin, 2019).

Table 8. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Master's Respondents in terms of Lifelong Learning*

	<i>Lifelong Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
	I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into learning process to boost their learning development, thus...		
1	I treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process.	4.08	Highly Committed
2	I embrace a student-like mindset and learning to turn self-education as a daily habit.	4.15	Highly Committed
3	I take courses outside of professional development and collaborate to discover creative teaching methods.	3.93	Highly Committed
4	I rely on experimentation and learning from experience to come up with new ways to teach and help learners grow.	3.96	Highly Committed
5	I set an example for my students by practicing what I teach.	4.21	Highly Committed
	Grand Mean:	4.07	Highly Committed

Legend: "Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50)," "Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50)," "Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50)," "Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50)," "Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 8 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents in terms of Lifelong Learning. The grand mean is 4.07 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly Committed." This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents. This implies that teachers were committed to a never-ending process of learning in their teaching job, professional development practices, or even in Graduate Schooling.

The highest item indicates that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their learning development, thus the respondents set an example for their students by practicing what they teach" with a mean rating of 4.21. This means that the respondents can be able to practice the theories and concepts learned in real-life problems.

This is followed by the statement showing that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their learning development, thus the respondents embrace a student-like mindset and learning to turn self-education as a daily habit" with a mean of 4.15.

This implies that the respondents thirst for knowledge and for Continuing Professional Education which is needed to graduate schooling. Ranking third was the indicator stating that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their learning development, thus the respondents treat mistakes and challenges as part of the learning process" with a mean of 4.08. This indicates that the respondents can accept mistakes and challenges and treat them as part of the learning process and be able to take learnings from them.

The lowest item shows that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their learning development, thus the respondents take courses outside of professional development and collaborate to discover creative teaching methods" with a mean of 3.93. This only shows that the respondents instilled lifelong learning and differentiated teaching methodologies to ensure learning outcomes.

These findings are about the supporting literature cited by Weerasinghe and Lalitha (2017) elaborating that satisfaction is a feeling of happiness that is obtained when a person fulfills his or her needs and desires. It is a state felt by a person who has experienced a performance or an outcome that fulfilled his or her expectations.

Accordingly, satisfaction can be defined as an experience of fulfillment of an expected outcome. The person will be satisfied when one achieves the expectations, hence it is a willful accomplishment that results in one's contentment. Satisfaction refers to the feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing perceived performance with the expectation. Customers will be satisfied when services fit with their expectations. Hence, it is a function of the relative level of expectation connecting with people's perceptions. When a person perceives the service encountered as good, he would be satisfied, on the other hand person will be dissatisfied when his or her perception crashes with the service expectation. Therefore, satisfaction is a perception of the pleasurable fulfillment of service.

Table 9. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Master's Respondents in terms of Application of Skills*

	<i>Application of Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
	I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that...		
1	I will be able to maintain my competencies in listening needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where I teach.	4.12	Highly Committed
2	I will be able to maintain my competencies in speaking needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where I teach.	4.06	Highly Committed
3	I will be able to maintain my competencies in writing needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where I teach.	4.00	Highly Committed
4	I will continuously nurture and enhance my competencies a self-directed researcher.	4.03	Highly Committed
5	I will continuously grow as a lifelong learner for the benefits of my learners.	4.23	Highly Committed
	Grand Mean:	4.09	Highly Committed

Legend: "Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50)," "Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50)," "Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50)," "Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50)," "Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 9 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents in terms of Application of Skills. The grand mean is 4.09 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly Committed." This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents. This implies that the teachers were committed to Graduate Schooling for Skills Development.

The highest rater indicates that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that the respondents will continuously grow as lifelong learners for the benefit of their learners" with a mean of 4.23. This means that the respondents have the drive to acquire Continuing Professional Education so that they can impart to their students what they know. This is followed by the indicator showing that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that the respondents will be able to maintain their competencies in listening needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where they teach" with a mean rating of 4.12. This implies that the respondents have the opportunity to apply and to use their professional competence as a Master's or a Doctorate holder in sharing with the school their expertise and experiences. Ranking third is the statement saying that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that the respondents will be able to maintain their competencies in speaking needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where they teach" with a mean of 4.06. This means that the respondents can be resource speakers in their school or even to other schools in imparting their knowledge and wisdom to the learners.

The lowest rater states that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that the respondents will be able to maintain their competencies in writing needed to become a successful graduate student and leader in the school where they teach" with a mean of 4.00. This shows that the respondents can harness their writing skills and be able to teach their students how to write in school or even to other entities where they can use it for their jobs or even for other purposes.

These findings are in line with the concepts and literature emphasizing that extensive research has been conducted on employees' satisfaction with work, but less is known about a construct of similar importance for students' lives, students' satisfaction with their academic studies. It is considered to be an important subjective educational outcome variable due to its relation to a wide range of crucial constructs such as stress tolerance, retention, and academic achievement (Wach, 2016). Student satisfaction is a key component of persistence and educational completion. Satisfied students are more likely to continue their educational path (Lumina, 2019). Satisfaction monitoring is based on studying student satisfaction feedback, which is a sign of successful performance for a higher educational institution. Student satisfaction feedback is defined as the opinions of students about the service they receive as students. This may include perceptions about the learning and teaching, the organization of the educational process, the learning support facilities, and the learning environment. International researchers agree that student feedback, which is assiduously collected in higher education institutions, will contribute to continuous education quality improvement (Tanova, 2018).

The highest indicator shows that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for written communication in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning" and "the respondents can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for comprehension in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning" with the same means of 4.31. This indicates that the respondents were able to practice their written communication and comprehension particularly when writing their Dissertation or even complying with the paper requirements in the graduate school. On the third rank is the statement saying that "the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for oral communication under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning" and "the respondents can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for statistics and interpretation of data under a highly specialized/and or

complex multidisciplinary field of learning” with the same means of 4.19. This implies that the respondents were able to apply their oral communication skills and skills in statistics and interpretation of data where their critical thinking and analysis were tested and applied.

Table 10. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Doctoral Respondents in terms of Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills*

<i>Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that...			
1	I can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for written communication in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.	4.31	Highly Committed
2	I can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for comprehension in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.	4.31	Highly Committed
3	I can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for oral communication under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.	4.19	Highly Committed
4	I can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for comprehension in the first language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.	4.06	Highly Committed
5	I can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for statistics and interpretation of data under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.	4.19	Highly Committed
Grand Mean:		4.21	Highly Committed

Legend: “Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50),” “Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50),” “Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50),” “Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)”

The lowest indicator states that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development so that the respondents can demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for comprehension in the first language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning” with a mean of 4.06. This shows that the comprehension or understanding and common sense of the respondents were tested in the graduate school including their analytical mind where they can develop new knowledge.

These results are in connection with the fact that students’ satisfaction is a short-term attitude, resulting from an evaluation of a student’s educational experiences. It is a positive antecedent of student loyalty and is the result and outcome of an educational system. Student satisfaction as students’ disposition by subjective evaluation of educational outcomes and experience. Therefore, student satisfaction can be defined as a function of the relative level of experiences and perceived performance in educational service during the study period. By considering all, students’ satisfaction can be defined as a short-term attitude resulting from an evaluation of students’ educational experience, services, and facilities (Weerasinghe & Lalitha, 2017).

Table 11. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Doctoral Respondents in terms of Utilization of Complex Research/Creative work and Professional Practice*

<i>Utilization of Complex Research/Creative work and Professional Practice</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice and /or the advancement of learning so that...			
1	I can diagnose research needs of my school, the immediate community, the country, and the world independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting.	4.25	Highly Committed
2	I can formulate research goals and objectives appropriate for the chosen topic independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting.	4.19	Highly Committed
3	I can identify resources needed for a research project independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting.	4.19	Highly Committed
4	I can choose and implement appropriate strategies needed for the completion of a research project independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting.	4.31	Highly Committed
5	I can evaluate the impact of research on the intended users and beneficiaries independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting.	4.13	Highly Committed
Grand Mean:		4.21	Highly Committed

Legend: “Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50),” “Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50),” “Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50),” “Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 11 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents in terms of Utilization of Complex Research/Creative work and Professional Practice. The grand mean is 4.21 with a verbal interpretation of “Highly Committed.” This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine

Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents. This implies that the teachers can utilize their research and the output or outcomes of the paper in the production of new ideas or knowledge in the school.

The highest response is on the statement showing that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice and /or the advancement of learning so that the respondents can choose and implement appropriate strategies needed for the completion of a research project independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting” with a mean of 4.31. This indicates that the respondents were made ready for interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary research project or setting. This was followed by the indicator showing that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice and /or the advancement of learning so that the respondents can diagnose research needs of their school, the immediate community, the country, and the world independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting” with a mean of 4.25. This shows that the respondents were able to assess the research needs of their school and how to resolve problems they felt apprehensive about. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice and/or the advancement of learning so that the respondents can formulate research goals and objectives appropriate for the chosen topic independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting” and “the respondents can identify resources needed for a research project independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting” with the same means of 4.19. This shows that the respondents can craft the research aims or objectives including the needed resources to conduct and implement the research project.

The lowest response states that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to take the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice and /or the advancement of learning so that the respondents can evaluate the impact of research on the intended users and beneficiaries independently or in teams of interdisciplinary or multidisciplinary setting” with a mean of 4.13. This implies that the respondents know the utilization of their research and how to implement and utilize it for the benefit of the many.

These findings are captured in the discussion of literature and studies that subsequently, investment in formal education does not come without a cost, and that cost is often not offset with the reward of a formal qualification when adult learners fail to persist. Deciding how much to invest in their education is one of the most important economic decisions people make during their lives (Hollinger & Larwin, 2019). Adult education participation is a means by which these adult students might accomplish their personal and professional goals, helping themselves, others, and society. In a general sense, adult education functions as a service. Adults come to adult education voluntarily, and for some programs, pay a registration fee to attend. Individuals invest in education because higher levels of schooling lead to higher income (Gallice & Grillo, 2018). Even without a registration fee, the cost of attending adult basic education minimally involves time, travel, and valuable resources for adults with other responsibilities. Framed in this manner, adult basic education students are investors (Hill, 2021).

Table 12. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Doctoral Respondents in terms of Application of More Complex Settings*

<i>Application of More Complex Settings</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I am committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying of more complex settings that demands leadership in research and creative work with strategic value added, thus...			
1	I can utilize research results to inform local practice.	4.25	Highly Committed
2	I can engage in professional learning.	4.44	Highly Committed
3	I can solve a problem or understand a process or phenomenon within a particular context.	4.31	Highly Committed
4	I can be empowered to generate self-knowledge.	4.38	Highly Committed
5	I can apply research findings in the context of our school operation.	4.25	Highly Committed
Grand Mean:		4.33	Highly Committed

Legend: “Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50),” “Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50),” “Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50),” “Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 12 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents in terms of the Application of More Complex Settings. The grand mean is 4.33 with a verbal interpretation of “Highly Committed.” This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents. This implies that the teachers can be able to apply the knowledge they have created or formed to the complex settings in the school.

The highest rater elicits that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying of more complex settings that demands leadership in research and creative work with strategic value-added, thus the respondents can engage in professional learning” with a mean of 4.44. This shows that the respondents were open with Continuing Professional Education as provided under the graduate schooling. Following is the statement stating that “the respondents are

committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying of more complex settings that demands leadership in research and creative work with strategic value-added, thus the respondents can be empowered to generate self-knowledge” with a mean rating of 4.38. This implies that the respondents have the opportunity for self-discovery and self-invention about the research project they are engaged with. Ranking third is the statement saying that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying of more complex settings that demands leadership in research and creative work with strategic value-added, thus the respondents can solve a problem or understand a process or phenomenon within a particular context” with a mean of 4.31. This implies that the respondents can understand a certain problem or phenomenon where research as a science can be applied and where the problem can be resolved.

The lowest rater indicates that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying of more complex settings that demands leadership in research and creative work with strategic value-added, thus the respondents can utilize research results to inform local practice” and “the respondents can apply research findings in the context of their school operation” with the same means of 4.25. This shows that the respondents could communicate the results of their research work to the community or locality and that they could apply these results to their school operation and be able to resolve the problems they felt or encountered.

These results are backed up or supported by the fact that equally important, completing a degree is a great accomplishment for the students and the culmination of years of hard work. At the same time, it served as evidence of meeting the mission of educating and graduating students. When a student enrolls in an academic program at an institution, both enter into a partnership intended to culminate with the student earning a degree awarded by the institution (Pullido, 2020). It may, therefore, be of value for graduate education to focus on offering learning experiences that foster student development, including research experiences, to support their research productivity, provide enriched learning experiences and curricula focused on their development as scholars to promote changes in the awareness of their professional skills, and to expand on the innovative ideas through research and apply ideas in a real-world context. Students understanding of the purpose of higher education, as well as exploring the roles to take as professionals, may help gain insight into their future careers, which may help sustain their roles as professionals upon graduation. As graduate students enter their fields to take roles that directly influence communities, it should become essential for them to develop an awareness of the significance of their positions and the level of social responsibility they should adhere (Choi & Choi, 2020).

Table 13. *Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development to Achieve Outcomes Articulated in Philippine Qualifications Framework of Doctoral Respondents in terms of Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability*

<i>Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I am committed to graduate schooling particularly in applying a significant level of expertise, so that:			
1	I can take leadership roles in the school and the community observing autonomy.	4.31	Highly Committed
2	I can take managerial roles in the school and the community ensuring much accountability.	4.31	Highly Committed
3	I can initiate changes in the school independently or in cooperation with others.	4.38	Highly Committed
4	I can pursue creative works such as research to expand the body of existing knowledge.	4.38	Highly Committed
5	I can be a role model in school, in the community and in the field.	4.25	Highly Committed
Grand Mean:		4.33	Highly Committed

Legend: “Not Committed (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Committed (1.51 – 2.50),” “Moderately Committed (2.51 – 3.50),” “Highly Committed (3.51 – 4.50),” “Very Highly Committed (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 13 shows the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents in terms of the Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability. The grand mean is 4.33 with a verbal interpretation of “Highly Committed.” This means that there is a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents. This implies that the teachers can be able to exert their expertise for professional development practices and for the transfer of learning in the school.

The highest item states that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling, particularly in applying a significant level of expertise so that the respondents can initiate changes in the school independently or in cooperation with others” and “the respondents can pursue creative works such as research to expand the body of existing knowledge” with the same means of 4.38. This means that the respondents cannot be resistant to change but rather embrace it and that they can contribute to the fund of knowledge given their research. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling, particularly in applying a significant level of expertise so that the respondents can take leadership roles in the school and the community observing autonomy” and “the respondents can take managerial roles in the school and the community ensuring much accountability” with the same means of 4.31. This implies that the respondents have the opportunity to lead or manage a research project or even a wider scope of work like the school.

The lowest item elicits that “the respondents are committed to graduate schooling particularly in applying a significant level of expertise, so that the respondents can be a role model in school, in the community and the field” with a mean of 4.25. This implies that

the respondents were allowed to become an exemplar or model to their students in the school.

These findings are based on factual data stating that graduate education has been the learning platform that provides various opportunities for students to engage in meaningful learning experiences for them to develop as socially responsible professionals. As professional identities progress as individuals gain insight into the development and actual practices of their professions, graduate students are provided with the opportunities to learn about professional identities including the attitudes, values, knowledge, beliefs, skills, and ways to provide service to the public as professionals may be meaningful (Choi & Choi, 2020).

3. Test for Significant Difference on the Level of Commitment of the Respondents to Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development when They are Grouped According to Profile

Table 14. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master’s Student Respondents when Grouped According to Age*

Indicators	Age (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	21-30	70.00	23.484	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	31-40	51.79				
	41-50	63.70				
	51-60	31.11				
Self-directed Research	21-30	75.82	28.953	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	31-40	50.78				
	41-50	62.33				
	51-60	28.33				
Lifelong Learning	21-30	73.28	31.051	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	31-40	49.50				
	41-50	62.11				
	51-60	24.50				
Application of Skills	21-30	70.57	26.764	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	31-40	52.10				
	41-50	62.37				
	51-60	25.28				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 14 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age. On advanced knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.000 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is statistically significant. In terms of Self-Directed Research, the p-value is 0.000 lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected in all. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is statistically significant. As to Lifelong Learning, the p-value is 0.000 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is statistically significant. And, along with the application of skills, the p-value is 0.000 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is statistically significant.

Table 15. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test: Comparison on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling in terms of Advanced Skills and Knowledge and Self-Directed Research according to Age*

Age (in years)	Advanced Skills and Knowledge		Self-Directed Research	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
21-30 vs. 31-40	0.0137	Not Significant	0.0007	Significant
21-30 vs. 41-50	0.9720	Not Significant	0.1128	Not Significant
21-30 vs. 51-60	0.0019	Significant	0.0002	Significant
31-40 vs. 41-50	0.0340	Not Significant	0.1885	Not Significant
31-40 vs. 51-60	0.1024	Not Significant	0.0763	Not Significant
41-50 vs. 51-60	0.0034	Significant	0.0112	Not Significant

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 15 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age. On the advanced skills and knowledge, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 21-30 vs. 31-40, 21-30 vs. 41-50, 31-40 vs. 41-50, and 31-40 vs. 51-60. This means that significant differences do not lie in these ages for advanced skills and knowledge. This further implies that these are the ages where the master’s respondents do not have a high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional

development.

When it comes to self-directed research, the post ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction showed no significant differences between 21-30 vs. 41-50, 31-40 vs. 41-50, 31-40 vs. 51-60, and 41-50 and 51-60. This means that significant differences cannot be located in these ages for self-directed research. This further implies that these are the ages where the master's respondents have a low commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 16. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling when Grouped According to Age*

Age (in years)	Lifelong Learning		Application of Skills	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
21-30 vs. 31-40	0.0014	Significant	0.0843	Not Significant
21-30 vs. 41-50	0.7382	Not Significant	0.9722	Not Significant
21-30 vs. 51-60	0.0001	Significant	0.0004	Significant
31-40 vs. 41-50	0.0177	Not Significant	0.1475	Not Significant
31-40 vs. 51-60	0.0504	Not Significant	0.0067	Significant
41-50 vs. 51-60	0.0007	Significant	0.0008	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 16 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age. In terms of lifelong learning, the post-ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 21-30 vs. 41-50, 31-40 vs. 41-50, and 31-40 vs. 51-60. This means that significant differences are not observed in these ages for lifelong learning. This further implies that these are the ages where the master's respondents did not exert a higher level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Along with the application of skills, the Post Ad Hoc Test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 21-30 vs. 31-40, 21-30 vs. 41-50, and 31-40 vs. 41-50. This means that significant differences are not seen in these ages for the Application of Skills. This further implies that these are the ages where the master's respondents have no high level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 17. *Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master's Student Respondents when Grouped According to Sex*

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	Male	73.78	754.5	0.076	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	58.47				
Self-directed Research	Male	76.68	696.5	0.029	Reject Ho	Significant
	Female	57.90				
Lifelong Learning	Male	76.13	707.5	0.035	Reject Ho	Significant
	Female	58.00				
Application of Skills	Male	66.90	892.0	0.410	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	59.83				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 17 shows the Mann Whitney U-Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex. Along with the advanced knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.076 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. On the application of skills, the p-value is 0.410 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant.

On the other hand, when it comes to Self-Directed Research, the p-value is 0.029 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is statistically significant. By lifelong learning, the p-value is 0.035 lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is statistically significant.

Table 18 below shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status. On the advanced knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.410 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. As to the self-directed research, the p-value is 0.071 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected.

Table 18. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master’s Student Respondents Grouped According to Civil Status*

Indicators	Civil Status	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	Single	63.73	1.781	0.410	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	60.87				
	Widowed	35.50				
Self-directed Research	Single	71.94	5.281	0.071	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	57.78				
	Widowed	36.67				
Lifelong Learning	Single	69.56	6.615	0.037	Reject Ho	Significant
	Married	59.31				
	Widowed	18.00				
Application of Skills	Single	63.78	2.570	0.277	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	61.05				
	Widowed	29.83				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. Along with the application of skills, the p-value is 0.277 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant.

Table 19. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling when Grouped According to Civil Status*

Civil Status	Lifelong Learning	
	p-value	Remarks
Single vs. Married	0.1539	Not Significant
Single vs. Widowed	0.0139	Significant
Married vs. Widowed	0.0427	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 19 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status. According to lifelong learning, the post-ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant difference between single vs. married respondents. This means that significant differences do not lie in this civil status for Lifelong Learning. This further implies that this is the civil status where the master’s respondents exerted no higher level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 20. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master’s Student Respondents when Grouped According to Years in Service*

Indicators	Years in Service (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	0-5	59.50	9.021	.108	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	75.23				
	11-15	57.27				
	16-20	51.62				
	21-25	61.10				
	Over 26	39.60				
Self-directed Research	0-5	70.29	11.894	0.036	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10	65.58				
	11-15	55.17				
	16-20	52.78				
	21-25	57.90				
	Over 26	20.00				
Lifelong Learning	0-5	68.24	14.948	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10	67.27				
	11-15	52.80				
	16-20	56.90				
	21-25	60.80				
	Over 26	8.70				

Application of Skills	0-5	63.33	17.619	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10	75.15				
	11-15	55.00				
	16-20	55.66				
	21-25	54.50				
	Over 26	8.70				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 20 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. In terms of self-directed research, the p-value is 0.036 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is statistically significant. On lifelong learning, the p-value computed is 0.011 lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is statistically significant. Along with the application of skills the p-value is 0.003 smaller than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is statistically significant.

Table 21. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling when Grouped According to Years in Service*

Years in Service (in years)	Self-Directed Skills		Lifelong Learning	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
0-5 vs. 6-10	0.5690	Not Significant	0.9076	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 11-15	0.1478	Not Significant	0.1431	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 16-20	0.0469	Not Significant	0.2021	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 21-25	0.4915	Not Significant	0.7141	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 26 and above	0.0021	Significant	0.0003	Significant
6-10 vs. 11-15	0.3358	Not Significant	0.1849	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 16-20	0.1663	Not Significant	.2662	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 21-25	0.7120	Not Significant	.7660	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 26 and above	0.0060	Not Significant	0.0005	Significant
11-15 vs. 16-20	0.8318	Not Significant	0.7176	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 21-25	.07750	Not Significant	0.5562	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 26 and above	0.0477	Not Significant	0.0139	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 21-25	0.6481	Not Significant	0.7148	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 26 and above	0.0518	Not Significant	0.0046	Not Significant
21-25 vs. 26 and above	0.0553	Not Significant	0.0102	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 21 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. In self-directed Research, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant difference between 0-5 vs. 6-10, 0-5 vs. 11-15, 0-5 vs. 16-20, 0-5 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 11-15, 6-10 vs. 16-20, 6-10 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 26 and above, 11-15 vs. 16-20, 11-15 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 26 and above, 16-20 vs. 21-25, 16-20 vs. 26 and above, and 21-25 vs. 26 and above. This means that significant differences cannot be located in the length of experiences of teachers for self-directed research. This further implies that these are the longevity of services where the master’s respondents applied a low level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

When it comes to lifelong learning, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 0-5 vs. 6-10, 0-5 vs. 11-15, 0-5 vs. 16-20, 0-5 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 11-15, 6-10 vs. 16-20, 6-10 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 16-20, 11-15 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 26 and above, 16-20 vs. 21-25, 16-20 vs. 26 and above, and 21-25 vs. 26 and above. This means that significant differences were not reflected in the length of experiences of teachers for lifelong learning. This further implies that these are the longevity of services where the master’s respondents gained a dull level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 22 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. Along with the application of skills, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 0-5 vs. 6-10, 0-5 vs. 11-15, 0-5 vs. 16-20, 0-5 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 11-15, 6-10 vs. 16-20, 6-10 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 16-20, 11-15 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 26 and above, 16-20 vs. 21-25, 16-20 vs. 26 and above, and 21-25 vs. 26 and above. This means that significant differences did not lie in the length of experiences of teachers for the application of skills. This further implies that these are the longevity of services where the master’s respondents acquired a poor level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 22. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling when Grouped According to Years in Service*

Years in Service (in years)	Application of Skills	
	p-value	Remarks
0-5 vs. 6-10	0.1556	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 11-15	0.4275	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 16-20	0.3863	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 21-25	0.5201	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 26 and above	0.0009	Significant
6-10 vs. 11-15	0.0639	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 16-20	0.0360	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 21-25	0.1620	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 26 and above	0.0000	Significant
11-15 vs. 16-20	0.9534	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 21-25	0.9324	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 26 and above	0.0095	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 21-25	0.8949	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 26 and above	0.0056	Not Significant
21-25 vs. 26 and above	0.0320	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 23 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation. With the advanced knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.231 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. As to self-directed research, the p-value is 0.201 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected.

Table 23. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master’s Student Respondents when Grouped According to Designation*

Indicators	Designation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	Teacher 1	65.60	5.598	0.231	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	58.40				
	Teacher 3	51.61				
	Master Teacher 1	48.50				
	Master Teacher 2	6.00				
Self-directed Research	Teacher 1	65.48	5.980	0.201	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	55.96				
	Teacher 3	46.68				
	Master Teacher 1	81.67				
	Master Teacher 2	70.00				
Lifelong Learning	Teacher 1	64.80	3.612	0.461	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	59.38				
	Teacher 3	48.26				
	Master Teacher 1	66.67				
	Master Teacher 2	49.00				
Application of Skills	Teacher 1	64.24	5.349	0.253	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	62.70				
	Teacher 3	44.24				
	Master Teacher 1	69.83				
	Master Teacher 2	74.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. As regards lifelong learning, the p-value is 0.461 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. Along with the application of skills, the p-value is 0.253 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant.

Table 24. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Master’s Student Respondents when Grouped According to Units Earned*

Indicators	Units Earned	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Advanced Knowledge and Skills	0-9 units	68.45	9.183	0.102	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	10-18 units	61.83				
	19-27 units	38.07				
	28-36 units	67.05				
	37-45 units	61.96				
Self-directed Research	46 units and above	51.28	5.329	0.387	Failed Reject Ho	Not Significant
	0-9 units	57.80				
	10-18 units	59.83				
	19-27 units	43.27				
	28-36 units	66.42				
Lifelong Learning	37-45 units	61.00	13.778	0.017	Reject Ho	Significant
	46 units and above	62.78				
	0-9 units	57.90				
	10-18 units	66.00				
	19-27 units	30.13				
Application of Skills	28-36 units	66.21	17.779	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
	37-45 units	66.54				
	46 units and above	64.83				
	0-9 units	43.80				
	10-18 units	66.94				
	19-27 units	29.83				
	28-36 units	67.46				
	37-45 units	67.31				
	46 units and above	70.50				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 24 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned. According to the advanced knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.102 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. In relation to the self-directed research, the p-value is 0.387 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant.

On the other hand, when it comes to lifelong learning, the p-value is 0.017 less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is statistically significant. As regards the application of skills, the p-value is 0.003 smaller than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master’s respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is statistically significant.

Table 25. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling when Grouped According to Units Earned*

Units Earned	Lifelong Learning		Application of Skills	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
0-9 units vs. 10-18 units	0.6115	Not Significant	0.1451	Not Significant
0-9 units vs. 19-27 units	0.0501	Not Significant	0.3223	Not Significant
0-9 units vs. 28-35 units	0.4867	Not Significant	0.0468	Not Significant
0-9 units vs. 36-45 units	0.5083	Not Significant	0.0707	Not Significant
0-9 units vs. 46 units and above	0.6638	Not Significant	0.0928	Not Significant
10-18 units vs. 19-27 units	0.0143	Not Significant	0.0109	Not Significant
10-18 units vs. 28-35 units	0.9864	Not Significant	0.9668	Not Significant
10-18 units vs. 36-45 units	0.9682	Not Significant	0.9783	Not Significant
10-18 units vs. 46 units and above	0.9432	Not Significant	0.8273	Not Significant
19-27 units vs. 28-35 units	0.0004	Significant	0.0002	Significant
19-27 units vs. 36-45 units	0.0014	Significant	0.0010	Significant
19-27 units vs. 46 units and above	0.0178	Not Significant	0.0053	Not Significant
28-35 units vs. 36-45 units	0.9692	Not Significant	0.9858	Not Significant

Units Earned	Lifelong Learning		Application of Skills	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
28-35 units vs. 46 units and above	0.9121	Not Significant	0.8072	Not Significant
36-45 units vs. 46 units and above	0.8998	Not Significant	0.8135	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 25 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies on the level of graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned. On lifelong learning, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 0-9 vs. 10-18, 0-9 vs. 19-27, 0-9 vs. 28-35, 0-9 vs.36-45, 0-9 vs. 46 and above, 10-18 vs. 19-27, 10-18 vs. 28-35, 10-18 vs. 36-45, 10-18 vs. 46 and above, 19-27 vs. 46 and above, 28-35 vs. 36-45, 28-35 vs. 46 and above, and 36-45 vs. 46 and above. This means that significant differences were not seen in these units enrolled by teachers for lifelong learning. This further implies that there are several units required to be enrolled in graduate schooling where the master’s respondents received an inadequate level of commitment to graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 26. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents when Grouped According to Age*

Indicators	Age (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	21-30	8.50	0.916	0.821	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	8.96				
	41-50	5.50				
	51-60	5.50				
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	21-30	14.50	2.382	0.497	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	8.50				
	41-50	4.00				
	51-60	5.50				
Application of More Complex Settings	21-30	7.00	1.665	0.645	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	9.19				
	41-50	4.00				
	51-60	5.00				
Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	21-30	11.00	1.812	0.612	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	8.92				
	41-50	4.00				
	51-60	5.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 26 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age. According to the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.821 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. As to the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.497 greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. In terms of the application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.645 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. Lastly, in accordance with the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.612 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant.

Table 27 shows the Mann Whitney U – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex. Along with the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.186 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. In terms of the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.112 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. As regards the application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.368 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant.

Table 27. *Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents as a Professional Development when Grouped According to Sex*

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	Male	10.29	19.0	0.186	Failed to	Not
	Female	7.11			Reject Ho	Significant
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	Male	10.64	16.5	0.112	Failed to	Not
	Female	6.83			Reject Ho	Significant
Application of More Complex Settings	Male	9.71	23.0	0.368	Failed to	Not
	Female	7.56			Reject Ho	Significant
Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	Male	8.21	33.5	0.832	Failed to	Not
	Female	8.72			Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

As to the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.832 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant.

Table 28. *Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents when Grouped According to Civil Status*

Indicators	Civil Status	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	Single	5.75	13.5	0.075	Failed to	Not
	Married	10.15			Reject Ho	Significant
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	Single	6.33	17.0	0.159	Failed to	Not
	Married	9.80			Reject Ho	Significant
Application of More Complex Settings	Single	6.67	19.0	0.233	Failed to	Not
	Married	9.60			Reject Ho	Significant
Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	Single	7.33	23.0	0.448	Failed to	Not
	Married	9.20			Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 28 below shows the Mann Whitney U – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status. As to the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.075 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. On utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.159 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected.

The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. As regards with application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.233 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. In accordance with the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.448 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant.

Table 29 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. On the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.069 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant.

As to the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.064 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. As regards the application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.236 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. When it comes to the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.832 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant.

Table 29. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents when Grouped According to Years in Service*

Indicators	Years in Service (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	6-10	8.50	7.081	0.069	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	11-15	15.00				
	21-25	7.00				
	Over 26	5.50				
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	6-10	14.00	7.251	0.064	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	11-15	14.00				
	21-25	6.82				
	Over 26	5.00				
Application of More Complex Settings	6-10	7.00	4.247	0.236	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	11-15	13.50				
	21-25	7.55				
	Over 26	5.50				
Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	6-10	11.00	0.874	0.832	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	11-15	8.00				
	21-25	8.73				
	Over 26	5.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 30 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation. As to the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.485 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant.

Table 30. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents when Grouped According to Designation*

Indicators	Designation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	Teacher 2	3.00	1.446	0.485	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	8.96				
	Master Teacher 1	8.50				
	Master Teacher 2	8.50				
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	Teacher 2	3.00	2.237	0.327	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	8.83				
	Master Teacher 1	10.75				
	Master Teacher 2	5.50				
Application of More Complex Settings	Teacher 2	3.00	3.063	0.216	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	8.13				
	Master Teacher 1	11.00				
	Master Teacher 2	13.50				
Application of Significant Level Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	Teacher 2	1.00	5.607	0.061	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 3	8.08				
	Master Teacher 1	11.00				
	Master Teacher 2	16.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

As regards the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.327 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. In accordance with the application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.216 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected.

The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. And, in terms of the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.061 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant.

Table 31. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Level of Commitment to Graduate Schooling of Doctoral Student Respondents when Grouped According to Units Earned*

Indicators	Units Earned	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Demonstration of Highly Systematic Knowledge and Skills	10-18 units	5.00	2.683	0.261	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	19-27 units	8.50				
	28-36 units	6.88				
	37-45 units	10.88				
	46 units and above	9.30				
Utilization of Complex Research/Creative Work and Professional Practice	10-18 units	8.00	0.829	0.661	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	19-27 units	5.50				
	28-36 units	7.75				
	37-45 units	9.75				
	46 units and above	8.90				
Application of More Complex Settings	10-18 units	4.25	3.389	0.184	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	19-27 units	13.50				
	28-36 units	7.25				
	37-45 units	9.00				
	46 units and above	9.80				
Application of Significant Level of Expertise-Based Autonomy and Accountability	10-18 units	6.75	3.824	0.148	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	19-27 units	16.00				
	28-36 units	6.63				
	37-45 units	10.00				
	46 units and above	8.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 31 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned. On the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, the p-value is 0.261 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. In accordance with the utilization of complex research/creative work and professional practice, the p-value is 0.661 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. As to the application of more complex settings, the p-value is 0.184 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. And, when it comes to the application of a significant level of expertise-based autonomy and accountability, the p-value is 0.148 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant.

4. Encountered Difficulties in Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development

Table 32. *Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students in terms of Financing the Study*

	Financing the Study	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I lack financial resources.	3.75	Often Encountered
2	I have no sufficient scholarships.	3.82	Often Encountered
3	I encountered costly school fees.	3.69	Often Encountered
4	I lack financial assistance.	3.86	Often Encountered
5	I have a conflict between the family’s budget and school fees.	3.88	Often Encountered
Grand Mean:		3.80	Often Encountered

Legend: "Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)," "Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)," "Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)," "Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)," "Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 32 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of financing the Study. The grand mean is 3.80 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education.

The highest indicator shows that “the respondents have a conflict between the family’s budget and school fees” with a mean of 3.88. This means that the respondents have problems with budget allocation between family expenses and the school fees incurred. Next was the indicator stating that “the respondents lack financial assistance” with a mean of 3.86. This means that the respondents lack the skills

to find financial assistance, scholarships, financial grants, or financial aid to pursue their graduate schooling and study. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents have no sufficient scholarships” with a mean of 3.82. This implies that the respondents had no scholarship grants or any financial aid.

The lowest indicator states that “the respondents encountered costly school fees” with a mean of 3.69. This shows that the respondents have expensive fees in the school.

These results are aligned with the fact that graduate students are more likely to finance their education rather than rely on family assistance (Bednar & Gicheva, 2013; Elliot & Friedline, 2013). Difficulty in financing education is a common theme for all student groups, however, dealing with competing financial priorities can add difficulty for students pursuing higher education. Graduate tuition can be prohibitively expensive, and there are fewer loans and scholarship grants available to graduate students.

At first point, it is easy for students to move from undergraduate to graduate study but then again there are salient factors that could affect students’ performance in graduate school (Badidles, 2021). Adult learners must contend with several competing realities while pursuing their credentials. They are often working full-time or multiple jobs. They have families, financial obligations, and additional responsibilities competing for their time and attention (Lumina, 2019).

Also, graduate students are expected to participate in the game of academic enculturation. They face challenges and struggles in textual, social, and political arenas. Learning in and from graduate school requires more than just intelligence, strategic social, cultural, and political participation, and constructing a professional identity are at least as important. Academics have adequate priorities like family, friends, et cetera. Unsatisfactory combinations of work and home duties can result in various unfavorable individual and organizational outcomes for scholars (Putnik, et al. 2018).

Table 33. Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students in terms of School Requirements

	<i>School Requirements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	I have too many school requirements.	3.73	Often Encountered
2	I have insufficient time doing school requirements.	3.75	Often Encountered
3	I have difficulties in accomplishing technically demanding requirements.	3.67	Often Encountered
4	I have problems completing requirements due to ICT limitation.	3.12	Seldom Encountered
5	I am pressured to accomplish additional work/assignments.	3.75	Often Encountered
	Grand Mean:	3.60	Often Encountered

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50),” “Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50),” “Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50),” “Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 33 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of school requirements. The grand mean is 3.60 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education.

The highest item reveals that “the respondents have insufficient time doing school requirements” and “the respondents are pressured to accomplish additional work/assignments” with the same means of 3.75. This indicates that the respondents have good time management and that they experience time pressures in doing their school work. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents have too many school requirements” with a mean of 3.73. This means that the respondents have more responsibilities in school having too many requirements to submit.

The lowest item states that “the respondents have problems completing requirements due to ICT limitation” with a mean of 3.12. This implies that the respondents experienced problems in completing their requirements because of ICT technicalities.

These results are in connection with the literature that it is very apparent that graduate students face different challenges in their studies, priorities, responsibilities, pressure, and ability to cope with problems and stress. These are big factors that affect commitment to finish their master’s degree (Badidles, 2021). Students’ priority talks about their ability to allocate limited time for bulk urgencies. One must think that more important things must be done or dealt with first depending on its weight one at a time to achieve success. Responsibilities refer to graduate students’ duties or tasks that they are required or expected to do. With these immense and equally important roles of a graduate student, they need to be extra driven to fulfill all the parts. The pressure exerted on the students comes from the urge to balance financial obligations, the drive to pass examinations, and the need to finish their research outputs. The student’s ability to cope with very stressful situations in school, home, and work is needed. Their ability to cope with stress will lead to acceptance and more eagerness to finish their studies or drop out of school. It is tested especially when they are to take examinations, comply with responsibilities in the workplace, and face family issues all at the same time. Research findings show that students who cannot handle stress and balance time towards work, home, and studies have a lesser chance of finishing their graduate studies (Badidles, 2021).

Table 34 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of family commitments while going to school. This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education.

The highest response is on the item stating that “the respondents have too many responsibilities at home” with a mean of 3.89. This indicates that the respondents may have too many household chores and activities at home. This is followed by the indicator showing

that “the respondents have constraints between study time and family time” with a mean of 3.87. This showed that the respondents have problems balancing their time and how to achieve it to the fullest. Ranking third is the statement indicating that “the respondents have family and parenting obligations” with a mean of 3.86. This shows that the respondents were family-oriented people having responsibilities as parents.

Table 34. *Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students in terms of Family Commitments while Going to School*

	<i>Family Commitments while Going to School</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	I have family and parenting obligations.	3.86	Often Encountered
2	I have too many responsibilities at home.	3.89	Often Encountered
3	I have constraints between study time and family time.	3.87	Often Encountered
4	I have competing priorities between academic study and home responsibilities.	3.83	Often Encountered
5	I have difficulty in balancing education and family life.	3.69	Often Encountered
Grand Mean:		3.83	Often Encountered

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50),” “Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50),” “Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50),” “Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)”

The lowest response states that “the respondents have difficulty in balancing education and family life” with a mean of 3.69. This shows that the respondents have difficulty balancing their time between family life and education where they have spent their days.

These findings are about the concepts and literature that being a teacher and a student at the same time is advantageous in that they can apply the information and the experience acquired during graduate education in the school. However, Calisuglo and Yalvac (2019) argue that the downside of being a teacher and student at the same time is that it is a difficult and exhausting process, and they have time problems. The study of Sayan and Aksu (2019) determines that wearing more than one hat, economic problems, and being unable to spare enough time cause a decrease in efficiency and energy.

Oloya (2016) in his study points out personal-related, family-related, and school-related factors problems usually experienced by working students. A common struggle for graduate students is balancing work, life, and school. Martinez, Ordu, Della Sala, and McFarlane (2013) explore how difficult it can be for students to be successful in school and maintain a balance between school, on-campus work, and life. These studies show that these factors harm graduate students because they add priorities that compete with the graduate student’s academic study. Morris (2013) states that there is already tension between work and family and that this tension could be worse if the person is studying. The main sources of tension could be time available, family and social interactions, personal priorities, and financial constraints (Morris, 2013; Duke & Hinzen, 2014).

Table 35. *Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students in terms of Thesis Requirements*

	<i>Thesis Requirements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	I have inadequate knowledge of research/thesis writing.	3.35	Seldom Encountered
2	I have insufficient time to complete thesis requirements.	3.73	Often Encountered
3	I have costly thesis fees and expenses.	3.99	Often Encountered
4	I lack research/thesis skills.	3.29	Seldom Encountered
5	I lack guidance and support to conduct a study.	3.29	Seldom Encountered
Grand Mean:		3.53	Often Encountered

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50),” “Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50),” “Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50),” “Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50),” “Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 35 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of thesis requirements. The grand mean is 3.53 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education.

The highest indicator states that “the respondents have costly thesis fees and expenses” with a mean of 3.99. This indicates that the respondents have expensive fees for their thesis study. Following is the statement indicating that “the respondents have insufficient time to complete thesis requirements” with a mean of 3.73. This only shows that the respondents had less time to complete their thesis requirements given that they have varied responsibilities. On the third rank is the statement indicating that “the respondents have inadequate knowledge of research/thesis writing” with a mean of 3.35. This implies that the respondents had little knowledge or no knowledge of research/thesis writing.

The lowest indicator states that “the respondents lack research/thesis skills” and “the respondents lack guidance and support to conduct a study” with the same means of 3.29. This elicits that the respondents have no skills in research and that they have no coach or mentor to guide them aside from the assigned thesis adviser. These results are in line with the idea and studies that the demands of graduate school are higher than those of college. Some graduate education students consider not finishing graduate school because they realize that the degree does not support their long-term goals (Aypay, 2016). They do not finish the degree because they are not smart enough to finish. Rather, many students are not able to manage their projects or integrate into the academic lifestyle (Gordon, 2016). Without the right project management skills, students feel overwhelmed and burned out most of the time (Farkas, 2018).

While on the path toward an idealized future, graduate students face unique challenges and stressors, such as those emerging from financial burdens, supervisory relationships, and scholastic pressure (e.g., publish or perish, tenure or you have settled), that can have a negative impact on student retention and overall well-being (Evans et al., 2018). Indeed, graduate students have been found to have such high levels of distress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues that it has been described as a mental health crisis and efforts to investigate and support the creation of thriving-supportive learning environments have been labeled a necessity (Charles et al., 2021; Posselt, 2021). As graduate programs continue to experience tremendous growth the need to address systemic pressures that can impact student well-being and support students in their ability to thrive within their programs of study becomes ever more important.

Table 36. Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate in terms of Balancing Work and Study

	Balancing Work and Study	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I have conflicts between work demands and university requirements.	3.71	Often Encountered
2	I have too many ancillaries / workloads in school.	3.73	Often Encountered
3	I have difficulty fulfilling the responsibilities of being a teacher while fulfilling the responsibilities of being a student.	3.76	Often Encountered
4	I have an inability to create a balance between education and work.	3.54	Often Encountered
5	I have difficulty in time management.	3.55	Often Encountered
Grand Mean:		3.65	Often Encountered

Legend: "Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)," "Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)," "Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)," "Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)," "Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 36 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of balancing work and study. The grand mean is 3.65 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education. The highest item shows that “the respondents have difficulty fulfilling the responsibilities of being a teacher while fulfilling the responsibilities of being a student” with a mean of 3.76. This shows that the respondents have difficulty in fulfilling their responsibilities as teacher and as a graduate student. The next indicator shows that “the respondents have too many ancillaries/workloads in school” with a mean of 3.73. This indicates that the respondents had too much work to do in school. Ranking third is the statement eliciting that “the respondents have conflicts between work demands and university requirements” with a mean of 3.71. This indicates that the respondents have difficulty finding time for work demands and at the same time fulfilling their university requirements. The lowest item shows that “the respondents cannot create a balance between education and work” with a mean of 3.54. This shows that the respondents have difficulty in allocating their time between education and work since both demand time consumption and quality time.

These findings are in line with the fact that the graduate student experience is a time-intensive struggle of balancing work, life, and the demands of multiple roles (Blanchard & Haccoun, 2020; Lorusso et al., 2020). Students’ perceived ability to balance academic and non-academic undertakings can have an impact on their self-efficacy (Yusuf et al., 2020) and resourcefulness (Reed & Kennett, 2017), as well as their mental health (Sprung & Rogers, 2020). Relatedly, access to adequate funding has been shown to impact program completion and students’ ability to engage in important academic tasks, such as publishing. Financial instability, anxiety associated with time to completion, workload, access to career development opportunities, campus culture, and availability and access to support mechanisms have all been found to impact the graduate student experience (McAlpine & Austin, 2019; Ahn & Davis, 2020). Moreover, students encounter these various stressors in tandem with the mandatory requirements of rigorous academic programs (Breen, 2019) such as comprehensive examinations and thesis defense, while also functioning within a higher education environment that calls for high student productivity (Coe-Nesbitt et al., 2021).

Table 37. Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students in terms of Location of Graduate School

	Graduate School	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	The distance of graduate school is too far.	3.88	Often Encountered
2	I have costly transportation fees.	3.83	Often Encountered
3	I have no available transportation vehicles.	3.32	Seldom Encountered
4	I have exhausting and tiring travel to school.	3.67	Often Encountered
5	I have long hours of travelling time.	3.57	Often Encountered
Grand Mean:		3.65	Often Encountered

Legend: "Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)," "Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)," "Seldom Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)," "Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)," "Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 37 shows the respondent’s assessment of the difficulties encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education in terms of the Location of the Graduate School. The grand mean is 3.65 with a verbal interpretation of “Often Encountered.” This implies that the difficulties were often encountered by graduate students in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education.

The highest rater indicates that “the distance of graduate school is too far” with a mean of 3.88. This shows that the respondents have a far distance of the school from their home. Second in the rank is the statement saying that “the respondents have costly transportation

fees” with a mean of 3.83. This indicates that the respondents have expensive transportation fees. On the third rank is the statement saying that “the respondents have exhausting and tiring travel to school” with a mean of 3.67. This shows that traveling from home to school was a tiring part for the respondents. The lowest rater states that “the respondents have no available vehicles” with a mean of 3.32. This only shows that the respondents have no vehicle to use in going to school and that this poses an inaccessible or far location of the graduate school by the respondents. This means that the course offering or the program the respondents wanted to enroll in is in the school which is far away from the place of the respondents but this is not the case of PUP Open and Distance Learning since this school applied the Online Learning Instruction. However, the offline session does not become a burden or a problem to the PUP student in going to class for a face-to-face interaction.

The results are in line with the fact that the study of Calisuglo and Yalvac (2019) conducted to determine the problems the teachers encounter in their master’s degree, found out that the major problem that the participants experience is the distance between the school and the university. The root of this problem is because the city where they work and the city where they take graduate education are different cities. It is also seen that the conflict between their schedule in school and their schedule in graduate education causes problems.

5. Test for Significant Difference on the Difficulties Encountered by the Respondents in Pursuing Graduate Schooling as a Professional Development when they are Grouped According to Profile

Table 38. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Age*

Indicators	Age (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	21-30	73.98	4.753	0.191	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	67.10				
	41-50	73.12				
	51-60	45.15				
School Requirements	21-30	70.34	0.794	0.851	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	65.56				
	41-50	71.31				
	51-60	75.25				
Family Commitments while Going to School	21-30	61.73	3.799	0.284	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	69.46				
	41-50	75.04				
	51-60	84.95				
Thesis Requirements	21-30	70.10	0.208	0.976	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	67.09				
	41-50	70.35				
	51-60	70.65				
Balancing Work and Study	21-30	62.41	2.509	0.474	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	70.91				
	41-50	72.35				
	51-60	80.95				
Location of Graduate School	21-30	74.41	2.340	0.505	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-40	64.58				
	41-50	64.90				
	51-60	78.05				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 38 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age. On financing the study, the p-value is 0.191 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. As to school requirements, the p-value is 0.851 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. As regards family commitments while going to school, the p-value is 0.284 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. When it comes to thesis requirements, the p-value is 0.976 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant. In terms of balancing work and study, the p-value is 0.474 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped

according to age is not statistically significant. And, along with the location of graduate school, the p-value is 0.505 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant.

Table 39. Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Sex

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	Male	33.76	1424.5	0.743	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	69.55				
School Requirements	Male	77.48	1256.0	0.215	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	66.92				
Family Commitments while Going to School	Male	72.76	1383.5	0.583	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	68.08				
Thesis Requirements	Male	70.28	1344.0	0.445	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	63.78				
Balancing Work and Study	Male	78.91	1217.5	0.148	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	66.57				
Location of Graduate School	Male	74.33	1341.0	0.436	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Female	67.69				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 39 shows the Mann Whitney U–Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex. In terms of financing the study, the p-value is 0.743 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. As to school requirements, the p-value is 0.215 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. Along with the family commitments, while going to school, the p-value is 0.583 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. As regards thesis requirements, the p-value is 0.445 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. When it comes to Balancing Work and Study, the p-value is 0.148 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant. On the Location of Graduate School, the p-value is 0.436 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant.

Table 40. Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Civil Status

Indicators	Civil Status	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	Single	76.70	4.469	0.107	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	64.93				
	Widowed	101.67				
School Requirements	Single	71.43	1.201	0.549	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	67.36				
	Widowed	90.67				
Family Commitments while Going to School	Single	53.21	8.372	0.015	Reject Ho	Significant
	Married	74.90				
	Widowed	80.17				
Thesis Requirements	Single	62.88	2.918	0.232	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	70.44				
	Widowed	100.50				
Balancing Work and Study	Single	59.50	4.008	0.135	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	71.94				
	Widowed	95.17				
Location of Graduate School	Single	75.58	2.562	0.278	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Married	65.73				
	Widowed	90.33				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 40 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status. According to financing the study, the p-value is 0.107 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. As to school requirements, the p-value is 0.549 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. In terms of thesis requirements, the p-value is 0.232 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. Along with balancing work and study, the p-value is 0.135 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant. As regards with location of the graduate school, the p-value is 0.278 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status is not statistically significant.

Table 41. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Civil Status*

Civil Status	Family Commitments while Going to School	
	p-value	Remarks
Single vs. Married	0.0040	Significant
Single vs. Widowed	0.2535	Not Significant
Married vs. Widowed	0.8195	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/3 =0.0167) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 41 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies in the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to civil status. On family commitments, while going to school, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant difference between single and widowed; and married and widowed. This means that significant differences did not lie in the civil status of teachers to family commitments while going to school. This further implied that the civil status of the respondents where the doctoral respondents encountered more difficulties in pursuing graduate Schooling as a professional development.

Table 42. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison of the Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Years in Service*

Indicators	Years in Service (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	0-5	73.30	1.076	0.956	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	69.21				
	11-15	64.56				
	16-20	65.46				
	21-25	73.58				
	Over 26	68.58				
School Requirements	0-5	63.68	5.105	0.403	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	67.69				
	11-15	64.83				
	16-20	74.08				
	21-25	66.00				
	Over 26	99.92				
Family Commitments while Going to School	0-5	54.51	16.505	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10	76.87				
	11-15	58.19				
	16-20	81.94				
	21-25	77.83				
	Over 26	105.08				
Thesis Requirements	0-5	63.69	8.899	0.113	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	69.49				
	11-15	57.15				
	16-20	80.66				
	21-25	71.17				
	Over 26	100.42				

Indicators	Years in Service (in years)	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Balancing Work and Study	0-5	57.86	10.243	0.069	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	74.79				
	11-15	59.52				
	16-20	79.76				
	21-25	81.08				
	Over 26	94.58				
Location of Graduate School	0-5	70.85	5.138	0.399	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10	71.59				
	11-15	60.60				
	16-20	64.50				
	21-25	67.25				
	Over 26	98.92				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 42 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. As to financing the study, the p-value is 0.956 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. In terms of school requirements, the p-value is 0.403 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. Along with Thesis Requirements, the p-value is 0.113 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. As regards balancing work and study, the p-value is 0.069 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant. In accordance with the location of graduate school, the p-value is 0.399 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service is not statistically significant.

Table 43. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped according to Years in Service*

Years in Service (in years)	Family Commitments while Going to School	
	p-value	Remarks
0-5 vs. 6-10	0.0149	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 11-15	0.7106	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 16-20	0.0063	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 21-25	0.1760	Not Significant
0-5 vs. 26 and above	0.0030	Significant
6-10 vs. 11-15	0.0686	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 16-20	0.6248	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 21-25	0.9558	Not Significant
6-10 vs. 26 and above	0.1055	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 16-20	0.0313	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 21-25	0.2706	Not Significant
11-15 vs. 26 and above	0.0085	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 21-25	0.8185	Not Significant
16-20 vs. 26 and above	0.1960	Not Significant
21-25 vs. 26 and above	0.2306	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/3 = 0.0167) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 43 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine where the significant difference lies in the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to years in service. When it comes to family commitments while going to school, the post ad hoc test using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni Correction shows no significant differences between 0-5 vs. 6-10, 0-5 vs. 11-15, 0-5 vs. 16-20, 0-5 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 11-15, 6-10 vs. 16-20, 6-10 vs. 21-25, 6-10 vs. 26 and above, 11-15 vs. 16-20, 11-15 vs. 21-25, 11-15 vs. 26 and above, 16-20 vs. 21-25, 16-20 vs. 26 and above, and 21-25 vs. 26 and above.

This means that significant differences cannot be located in these years in the service of teachers for family commitments while going to school. This further implies that in these years in service as teachers where the doctoral respondents experienced several difficulties in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development.

Table 44. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Assessment of Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Designation*

Indicators	Designation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	Teacher 1	72.64	2.951	0.566	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	69.90				
	Teacher 3	59.15				
	Master Teacher 1	77.20				
	Master Teacher 2	56.50				
School Requirements	Teacher 1	64.82	3.240	0.518	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	74.33				
	Teacher 3	70.24				
	Master Teacher 1	93.60				
	Master Teacher 2	71.75				
Family Commitments while Going to School	Teacher 1	66.21	2.808	0.590	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	68.21				
	Teacher 3	73.16				
	Master Teacher 1	93.30				
	Master Teacher 2	55.75				
Thesis Requirements	Teacher 1	72.45	2.805	0.591	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	69.77				
	Teacher 3	59.08				
	Master Teacher 1	78.30				
	Master Teacher 2	63.75				
Balancing Work and Study	Teacher 1	62.06	6.676	0.154	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	72.38				
	Teacher 3	83.21				
	Master Teacher 1	70.50				
	Master Teacher 2	54.25				
Location of Graduate School	Teacher 1	69.59	4.287	0.369	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher 2	68.96				
	Teacher 3	74.15				
	Master Teacher 1	42.70				
	Master Teacher 2	34.00				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 44 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation. On Financing the Study, the p-value is 0.566 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. As to school requirements, the p-value is 0.518 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. In terms of family commitments, while going to school, the p-value is 0.590 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. According to thesis requirements, the p-value is 0.591 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. As regards balancing work and study, the p-value is 0.154 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant. On the location of graduate School, the p-value is 0.369 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to designation is not statistically significant.

Table 45 shows the Kruskal – Wallis H – Test of the comparison on the assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned. On financing the study, the p-value is 0.412 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. As to school requirements, the p-value is 0.101 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected.

Table 45. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Assessment of the Difficulties Encountered by Graduate Students when Grouped According to Units Earned*

Indicators	Units Earned	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Financing the Study	0-9 units	43.15	5.028	0.412	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	10-18 units	73.73				
	19-27 units	76.28				
	28-36 units	70.16				
	37-45 units	70.36				
School Requirements	46 units and above	67.93	9.213	0.101	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	0-9 units	47.55				
	10-18 units	48.45				
	19-27 units	70.63				
	28-36 units	68.83				
Family Commitments while Going to School	37-45 units	82.45	7.101	0.213	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	46 units and above	72.43				
	0-9 units	50.80				
	10-18 units	59.32				
	19-27 units	76.41				
Thesis Requirements	28-36 units	68.92	4.005	0.549	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	37-45 units	81.05				
	46 units and above	57.36				
	0-9 units	54.80				
	10-18 units	80.91				
Balancing Work and Study	19-27 units	79.31	8.662	0.123	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	28-36 units	67.22				
	37-45 units	70.86				
	46 units and above	61.68				
	0-9 units	42.10				
Location of Graduate School	10-18 units	64.95	9.990	0.076	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	19-27 units	69.84				
	28-36 units	66.44				
	37-45 units	83.21				
	46 units and above	72.61				
	0-9 units	46.65				
	10-18 units	89.50				
	19-27 units	81.78				
	28-36 units	67.18				
	37-45 units	72.64				
	46 units and above	54.50				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. As to family commitments while going to school, the p-value is 0.213 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. In accordance with the thesis requirements, the p-value is 0.549 more than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. As regards balancing work and study, the p-value is 0.123 higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant. On the location of graduate school, the p-value is 0.076 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis fails to be rejected. The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to units earned is not statistically significant.

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived, the following conclusions were drawn:

Most of the respondents comprised mainly aged 31 to 40 years old, were female-dominated, married individuals, served the school for

0 to 5 years, were in the Teacher 1 position, and had earned 28 to 36 units.

Commitment to graduate schooling as professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of master's respondents was rated at a high level. On the application of skills, it revealed that the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to applying the abovementioned skills so that the respondents will continuously grow as lifelong learners for the benefit of their learners. When it comes to lifelong learning, it elicited that the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to incorporating new tools and strategies into the learning process to boost their learning development, thus the respondents set an example for their students by practicing what they teach. Similarly, commitment to graduate schooling as professional development to achieve outcomes articulated in the Philippine Qualifications Framework of doctoral respondents was also rated at a high level. In terms of the application of more complex settings, it elicited that the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development leading to the application of more complex settings that demand leadership in research and creative work with strategic value-added, thus the respondents can engage in professional learning. More so, for the demonstration of highly systematic knowledge and skills, it stated that the respondents are committed to graduate schooling as a means of professional development to demonstrate the highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for written communication in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning as well as demonstrate a highly advanced systematic knowledge and skills required for comprehension in a second language under a highly specialized/and or complex multidisciplinary field of learning.

The assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of master's respondents as a professional development when grouped according to profile is statistically significant except for civil status and designation which showed no statistically significant result. However, the assessment of the level of commitment to graduate schooling of doctoral respondents as a professional development when grouped according to profile is not statistically significant.

Graduate students often encountered difficulties in pursuing a graduate degree in Continuing Professional Education. On family commitments, while going to school, it stated that the respondents had too many responsibilities at home. According to the financing of the study, it showed that the respondents have a conflict between the family's budget and school fees. In terms of school requirements, it stated that the respondents had insufficient time doing school requirements as well as being pressured to accomplish additional work assignments. When it comes to thesis requirements, the respondents had costly thesis fees and expenses.

The assessment of the difficulties encountered in pursuing graduate schooling as a professional development when grouped according to age is not statistically significant except for civil status and years in service both under family commitments while going to School which showed statistically significant results.

References

- Admiraal, W. S. (2021). Schools as professional learning communities: what can schools do to support professional development of their teachers? *Prof. Dev. Educ.* 47, 684–698. doi:10.1080/19415257.2019.1665573
- Al-Jabari, B. (2019). Organizational commitment: a review of the conceptual and empirical literature and a research agenda. *International Leadership Journal*, 78-119.
- Alufohai, P. J. (2015). Influence of teachers' age, marital status and gender on students' academic achievement. *Asian Journal of Educational Research*. Vol. 3, 4, 1 - 7.
- Anderson, N. P. (2014). Innovation and creativity in organizations: a state-of-the-science review, prospective commentary, and guiding framework. *Journal of Management*, 40(5), 1297–1333. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206314527128>
- Antley, T. (2020, July 16). What is professional development and why is it important? Retrieved from WebCE: <https://www.webce.com/news/2020/07/16/professional-development>
- Badidles, W. K. (2021). Graduate life: a study on students' commitment towards professional development. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science*. Volume 26, Issue 2, Series 5, 6 - 11.
- Barlem, E. L. D. (2015, January - March). Satisfaction with academic experience among undergraduate nursing students. Retrieved from Scientific Electronic Library Online: <https://www.scielo.br/j/tce/a/QQzjpsmnpZ88XrRXqfYSRLD/?lang=en#:~:text=Academic%20satisfaction%20refers%20to%20the,expectations%20regarding%20their%20academic%20reality>.
- Berkhout, J. J. (2018). Context matters when striving to promote active and lifelong learning in medical education. *Med. Educ.*, 52, 34–44. doi:doi: 10.1111/medu.13463
- Blaney, J. W. (2022). Autonomy and privilege in doctoral education: an analysis of stem students' academic and professional trajectories. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 93(7), 1037-1063. doi:10.1080/00221546.2022.2082761
- Bourn, D. (2016). Teachers as agents of social change. *International Journal of Development Education and Global Learning*, 7(3), 63-

77. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1167813>

Brenner, C. A. (2022). Self-regulated learning, self-determination theory and teacher candidates' development of competency-based teaching practices. *Smart Learning Environment* (Springer Open).

Brookes, E. (2021, September 20). The theory of planned behavior. Retrieved from Simply Psychology: www.simplypsychology.org/theory-of-planned-behavior.html

Brown, T. (2018). Lifelong learning: an organising principle for reform. *Aust. J. Adult Learn*, 58, 312–335.

Burak, S. (2014). Motivation for instrument education: a study from the perspective of expectancy-value and flow theories. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*. Issue 55, 123-136.

Burak, S. (2014). Motivation for instrument education: a study from the perspective of expectancy-value and flow theories. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, Issue 55, 123-136.

Burns, A. & -H. (2014). Implementing action research in the modern language classroom. *Scottish Languages Review*, 27, 21-28.

Busatlic, S. (2018). Herzberg's two-factor theory of job satisfaction-comparative study between private and public high school teachers in Canton Sarajevo. *International Journal of Business Management & Research* Vol. 8, Issue 6, 27 - 48.

Campbell, K. (2023). What are the advantages of doing a postgraduate degree?

Chiu, T. K. (2022). Applying the self-determination theory (sdt) to explain student engagement in online learning during the covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 14-30.

Choi, J., & Choi, I. (2020). Exploring meaningful experiences promoting the development of graduate students' professionalism. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 32, 3, 388-401.

Coe-Nesbitt H. A., Soleas, E. K., Moucessian, A.M., Arghash, N., & Kutsyuruba, B. (2021, July 21). Conceptualizing thriving: an exploration of students' perceptions of positive functioning within graduate education. Retrieved from *Frontiers Education*: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2021.704135/full>

Collier, S. (2021, April 21). What is grad school? Retrieved from QS Top Universities: <https://www.topuniversities.com/blog/what-grad-school>

Commitment (n.d.). Retrieved from *Vocabulary.com*: <https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/>

Culatta, R. (2022). ANdragogy (Malcolm Knowles). Retrieved from *InstructionalDesign.org*: <https://www.instructionaldesign.org/theories/andragogy/>

Darling-Hammond, L. (2019, August 5). Investing for student success: lessons from state school finance reforms. Retrieved from *Learning Policy Institute*: <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/investing-student-success-school-finance-reforms-brief>

Davies, W. K. (2014). *Lifelong learning*. Abingdon: Taylor & Francis.

Demirel, M. (2017). Prospective teachers' lifelong learning tendencies and information literacy self-efficacy. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 12(6), 329–337.

Durak, H. (2018). Investigation of the contribution of coding training in teaching candidates to the development of lifelong learning competencies. *Journal of Ege Education Technologies*, 2(2), 55–67.

Dwivedula, R. (2010). The relation between organizational and professional commitment in case of project workers: implications for the project management. *Project Management Institute*.

El-Amin, A. (2020). Andragogy: a theory in practice in higher education. *Journal of Research in Higher Education*.

Freeman, A. K. (2017). *International encyclopedia of public health* (2nd Ed.): mental health and physical health (including HIV/AIDS). Academic Press.

Frostenson, M. (2015). Three forms of professional autonomy: de-professionalisation of teachers in a new light. *NordSTEP*, 1(28464). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.3402/nstep.v1.28464>

Gaikwad, C. E. (2015). The impact of andragogy on learning satisfaction of graduate students. *American Journal of Educational Research*. Vol. 3, No. 11, pp 1378-1386.

Gallice, A., & Grillo, E. (2018). A model of educational investment, social concerns and inequality. *Carlo Alberto Notebooks*.

Grant, A. H. (2020). A framework for graduated teacher autonomy: linking teacher proficiency with autonomy. *The Educational Forum*, 84(2), 100-113. doi:DOI: 10.1080/00131725.2020.1700324

- Grima-Farrell, C. (2017). What matters in a research to practice cycle? teachers as researchers. Springer Singapore: Springer Science+Business Media Singapore. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10->
- Habib, H. (2019). Professional commitment of secondary school teachers in relation to their self-efficacy. *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. 1, 35-38.
- Hagger, M. S. (2015). *Predicting and changing health behaviour: research and practice with social cognition models* (3rd Ed.). Maidenhead, UK: Open University Press.
- Hambre, V. J. (2020). Teachers' demographic profile on the learners' performance using k-12 earth and space module. *Journal of Education & Social Policy* .Vol. 7 No. 4, 1 - 11.
- Hansen, M. A. (2020). Social participation in the second half of life. 247-255. Academic Press.
- Hill, C. C. (2021). Exploring adult basic education student satisfaction: influencing factors and programmatic responses. Retrieved from The Institute for Habits and Minds: <https://www.habitsofmindinstitute.org/exploring-adult-basic-education-student-satisfaction-influencing-factors-and-programmatic-responses/>
- Hine, G. S. (2013). The importance of action research in teacher education programs. *Issues in Educational Research*, 23(2). Retrieved from <http://www.iier.org.au/iier23/hine.pdf>
- Hine, S. C. (2014). Action research: informing professional practice within schools. *Issues in Educational Research*, 24(2), 162-173. Retrieved from <http://www.iier.org.au/iier24/hine.html>
- Hollinger, J., & Larwin, K. (2019). Numeracy and adults' learning readiness and commitment: results from a large national random sample of participants. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 31, 3, 437-451.
- Hong, C. E. (2011). Action research in teacher education: classroom inquiry, reflection, and data-driven decision making. *Journal of Inquiry & Action in Education*, 4(2), 1-17. Retrieved from <http://www.wpunj.edu/dotAsset/330733.pd>
- Hunter, M. (2013). Skills, personal competencies and enterprise capabilities throughout the organization lifecycle. *Psychosocial. Issues Hum. Resour. Manag*, 1, 37-107.
- Human-Vogel, S., & Rabe, P. (2015). Measuring self-differentiation and academic commitment in university students: a case study of education and engineering students. *South African Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 45(1) 60-70.
- Hürsen, Ç. (2014). Are the teachers lifelong learners? *Procedia - social and behavioral sciences*. doi: 116. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1069.
- Hussen, A. A. (2021). Teachers professional commitment towards their students learning, the community and their profession. *Journal of Teacher Education and Educators*, 289-314.
- Ingvarson, L. (2017). Quality assurance in teacher education and outcomes: A study of 17 countries. *Educational Researcher*, 46(4), 177-193. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X17711900>
- Kaplan, H. (2021). Promoting optimal induction to beginning teachers using self-determination theory. *SAGE journals*, 1-14.
- Kowalczyk- W., M., & L., M. A. (2017). Teachers pursuing a doctoral degree: motivations and perceived impact.
- LaMorte, W. W. (2019, September 9). The theory of planned behavior. retrieved from Boston University School of Public Health: <https://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/mph-modules/sb/behavioralchangetheories/BehavioralChangeTheories3.html>
- Legault, L. (2017). The need for competence. *Research Gate*, 1-3.
- Letseka, M. A. (2021). The andragogical value of content knowledge method: the case of an adult education programme in Kwa-zulu Natal Province of South Africa. *Heliyon*, 2 - 7.
- Llego, M. (2022). 5 Reasons why teachers should pursue a master's degree in education.
- Lumina, R. N. (2019). National adult student satisfaction and priorities report. RNL0 and Lumina Foundation.
- Mahani, S. (2012). Enhancing the quality of teaching and learning through action research. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*. 9(3), 209-215. doi:<https://doi.org/10.19030/tlc.v9i3.708>
- Masood B. A. A. (2016). Perception of teachers' professional development needs, impacts, and barriers: The Abu Dhabi Case. *SAGE Open*, 1-15.
- McNiff, J. (2014). *Action research for professional development: concise advice for new and experienced action researchers*. Dorset: September Book. Ministry of National Education.

- Meriç, E. (2020). Prediction of professional commitment of teachers by the job characteristics of teaching profession. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 449-494.
- Miranda, P. (2021). Graduate teacher education in the philippines: observations and prospects. *The Normal Lights*. Vol. 14, 2, 1-25.
- Moore, L. (2022). How teachers can advance their careers with a doctorate in education.
- Morales, M. P. (2016). Participatory Action Research (PAR) cum Action Research (AR) in teacher professional development: a literature review. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*.
- Mugizi, W. (2015). Framework for the study of employee commitment. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 15-47.
- Ngala, F. W. (2017). The relationship between age of post-graduate adult learning students and learning style preferences: a case of africa international university, kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice* Vol.8, 8, 1 - 8.
- Ngidi, N. F. (2014, August 10). Electronic thesis and dissertations repository. retrieved from university of the Western Cape: <http://etd.uwc.ac.za/xmlui/handle/11394/4305>
- Owings, W., & Kaplan, L. (2019, August 9). Education as an investment in human capital.
- Özer, B. T. C. (2020). Development of an individual professional development plan proposal that is based on continuing professional development needs of teachers. *The European Educational Researcher*, 139-172.
- Pullido, V. S. (2020). Factors of graduate students' attrition and retention in Occidental Mindoro State College Graduate School. *International Journal of Educational Research & Social Sciences*.
- Ran, E. Y. (2020). Lifelong learning. Tel Aviv: Mofet.
- Rusbult, C. E., Martz, J. M., & Agnew, C. R. (n.d.). The investment model scale: measuring commitment level, satisfaction level, quality of alternatives, and investment size. *Personal Relationships*, 1998.
- Şahin, Z. &. (2018). An investigation on current trends in research on the use of web 2.0 technologies in the development of lifelong learning skills of adults. *Journal of Research*. 3(1), 23–34.
- Saad, N. M. (2018). Relationship between role conflict and job satisfaction among school leaders in secondary schools. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*. Vol., 7, 12, Pages 2954-2964.
- Scimago. (2019). Scimago journal and country rank. Retrieved from <https://www.scimagojr.com/countryrank.php?region=Asiatic%20Region>
- Siraneh, Y. S. O. (2018). Level and factors associated with professional commitment of health professionals providing institutional delivery services public health facilities, Southwest Ethiopia. *Ethiop J Health Sci.*, 495 - 504.
- Skaalvik, E. M. (2014). Teacher self-efficacy and perceived autonomy: relations with teacher engagement, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion. *Psychological Reports*, 114, 68-77.
- Smith, H. (2021). Why you should earn a doctorate.
- Soland, J. Z. (2019). Identifying naturally occurring direct assessments of social-emotional competencies: the promise and limitations of survey and assessment disengagement metadata. *Educ. Res*, 48, 466–478. doi:10.3102/0013189X19861
- Talukder, S. S. (2017). Influence of socio-demographic characteristics on academic performance of medical students. *Bangladesh Journal of Medical Education*. Vol.08 Issue 02, 1-6.
- Tan, S. K. (2013). Herzberg's two-factor theory on work motivation: does it works for todays environment? *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*. Vol. 2, 18 - 22.
- Tanova, A. E. (2018). Student satisfaction as an element of education quality monitoring in innovative higher education institution. *Web of Conferences*, Vol. 33.
- Tutor2u. (2018, April 8). Retrieved from *Relationships: Investment model*: <https://www.tutor2u.net/psychology/reference/relationships-investment-model>
- Tzanakou, C. (2014). The wider benefits of a PhD.
- Ulla, M. (2018). Benefits and challenges of doing research: experiences from philippine public school teachers. *Issues in Educational Research*, 28, 797-810.
- Ulla, M. B. (2017). Teacher training in Myanmar: teachers' perceptions and implications. *International. Journal of Instruction*, 10(2), 103-118. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1138329>

Ulla, M. B. (2021). Classroom teaching or academic publishing? An investigation of Philippine doctoral academics' beliefs. *Research in Education*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/00345237211024670>

Vamvaka, V. S. (2020). Attitude toward entrepreneurship, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention: dimensionality, structural relationships, and gender differences. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*.

Wach F-S, K. J. (2016). University students' satisfaction with their academic studies: personality and motivation matter. *Frontiers*. Retrieved from Frontier.

Walkington, H. S. (2020). Salient practices of award winning undergraduate research mentors — balancing freedom and control to achieve excellence. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(7), 1519-1532. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1637838>

Whitmyre, A. (2023). What are the advantages & disadvantages of getting a master's & a doctoral degree in education?

Weerasinghe, S., & Lalitha, S. F. (2017). Students' satisfaction in higher education literature review. *American Journal of Educational Research*, Vol. 5, No. 5, 533-539.

Young, M. (2015). *Family and work*. Elsevier.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Maureen V. Garcia

Salvacion Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines